

Perinatal Adverse events and Special Trends in Cognitive Trajectories (Plasticity-cohort).

First five-year Mortality, causes of death, and causes of severe disability resulting in exclusion from follow-up in the 1971 1974 birth cohort.

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1 Background

The birth cohort originates from Kätilöopisto maternity hospital, Helsinki, Finland. Children born in 1971–1974 fulfilling inclusion and exclusion criteria have been prospectively studied to adulthood.

The hospital is one of two major maternity hospitals, the other being the University Central Hospital, in the Helsinki metropolitan area with approximately 700000 residents at the time of enrollment. The hospital served as the primary maternity hospital serving an area of approximately 4,000km². Sixty percent of the mothers lived in Helsinki (mean distance to hospital 8 km), 7% in Espoo (distance 15 km), 15% in Vantaa (distance 14 km) and the remaining 15% in the surrounding municipalities (average distance to hospital 30 km) (Fig. 1). Children born in Kätilöopisto hospital therefore represent an unselected sample of deliveries within the area, with the exception of risk pregnancies due to maternal diabetes and known Rh-immunization, which the antenatal care centers referred directly to the university hospital. Deliveries with imminent complications were also referred to the University Central Hospital, if the clinical condition of the mother and the fetus permitted a transfer. Cesarean sections were performed both in the maternity hospital and in the university clinic. The two hospitals are located within a 10 minutes drive and worked in close cooperation. Resource demanding care, e.g. blood exchange transfusions and intensive care were given at the university hospital.

1.1 Births

There were 22,359 consecutive births, which at the time accounted for about 10% of all births in Finland and about one third in the province of Uusimaa, 2,113 (9.5%) were cesarean sections. Of these 1196 were enrolled.

1.2 Mortality

Of the 1196 infants, 160 died by the end of the 5th year of life, 141 / 160 of them (88 %) within 31 days post partum. The causes of death stratified by length of survival and birth weight are given in table 1. The cause of death was verified in autopsy in 130 cases. Autopsy was not done in 18 cases, 8 of which were severe malformations. It was not recorded in the remaining twelve cases whether an autopsy was performed or not.

1.3 Infant mortality rate 1971 – 1974 (deaths of < 1 years-of-age per 1000 live births)

The infant mortality rate is used as an indicator of the quality of prenatal and maternal care. Exemplary statistics from Finland and the United States of America are given for orientation.

Table 2. Infant mortality rate in Finland and USA

Year	Finland	USA
1970	13.2	20.0
1971	12.7	
1972	12.0	
1973	10.6	
1974	11.0	
1980	7.6	12.6

Table 1. Causes of death during the five first years in the 1971 1974 birth cohort

Time of death	Weight group	Pulmonary including IRDS	ICH and hydrocephalus	Malformations	Immaturity	Infection	Heart anomaly	Syndromes	Severe asphyxia	Missing data	Totals
< 24 hours	LBW < 1000 g	4			2						6
	LBW 1001 - 1500 g	3	3	1	2						9
	LBW 1501 - 2000 g	4	4		1	1					10
	> 2000 g	1	3	1		5	2	2	2		25
		21	1	2	5	6	2	2	2		50
1 - 6 days	LBW < 1000 g	9	1		4				1		15
	LBW 1001 - 1500 g	9	8	2	2				2		23
	LBW 1501 - 2000 g	2	2	6				3	1		14
	> 2000 g	11	4	5		3	4		1		28
		31	15	13	6	3	4	3	5		80
7 - 14 days	LBW < 1000 g				1						1
	LBW 1001 - 1500 g						1				1
	LBW 1501 - 2000 g					1	1				2
	> 2000 g	1		1			2	3			7
		1		1	1	1	4	3			11
15 - 31 days	Data missing									1	1
	LBW 1501 - 2000 g			1							1
	> 2000 g	1	2				1	1			5
		1	2	1			1	1		1	7
1 - 12 months	LBW < 1000 g				1						1
	LBW 1001 - 1500 g		1	1							2
	LBW 1501 - 2000 g					1					1
	> 2000 g	2		1		2					5
Total		2	1	2	1	3					9
12 - 59 months	> 2000 g						2		1		3
							2		1		3
Total		56	28	19	13	13	13	9	8	1	160

LBW = low birth weight, ICH = Intracerebral hemorrhage, IRDS = Idiopathic respiratory distress syndrome

2 Severe postnatal consequences leading to exclusion from follow-up study.

Infants with severe postnatal consequences identified in childhood (n=42) were excluded from follow-up. This included cases with mental/intellectual disability (n =26), cerebral palsy (n = 9), severe sensory impairment (hearing loss or blindness n = 7), see Table 2. Although hyperbilirubinemia was the risk factor which caused most recruitments in the study, no cases of kernicterus were recognized. G6PD deficiency is virtually nonexistent in Finland. Spherocytosis was suspected, but not confirmed in two cases.

Several excluded subjects did not have cognitive defects, e.g. subjects with cerebral palsy, blindness, and deafness. These subjects were excluded from further analyses because the study used methods that require at least partial vision, hearing and normal motor capabilities. However, many of these subjects were clinically followed.

The total number of subjects who died or were excluded due to severe consequences was 202.

Table 3. Main classes of causes and related factors for excluding 42 cases from subsequent analyses

Blindness	4
Retrolental fibroplasia	3
Rubeola syndrome	1
Cerebral palsy	9
Hemiparesis	2
Spastic diplegia	4
tetraplegia	2
Unknown	1
Deafness	3
Epilepsy	1
Hereditary	1
Hydrocephalus	1
Cognitive disability	26
Epilepsy + undefined syndrome	2
Brain atrophy, cause unknown	1
Down syndrome	5
Hydrocephalus	2
Hydrocephalus, deafness	1
Hypochondroplasia	1
Infantile spasm	1
Rubeola syndrome	2
tetraplegia	4
Unknown anomaly syndrome	4
Williams syndrome	1
Other	2
Total	42

